

PHILOSOPHICAL WORDS AND THE CONCEPT OF NATURE AND SOCIETY IN THE TRAGEDIES "MACBETH" AND "ABULFAYZ KHAN"

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KEY WORDS

Philosophical concepts of nature and society are important in examining the concept of man. Human life is directly connected with these two concepts-categories. In this process, there are a number of reasons that are not related to the human factor, and they are a decisive force in determining a person's lifestyle, happiness or unhappiness.

Speaking about the emergence of natural philosophy, it should first be noted that it is a product of the development of Renaissance culture and humanist philosophy. At such a turning point in the world civilization, a person opened new perspectives for himself, in particular, he began to believe that new opportunities have arisen to strengthen his place in the world, freedom in his creative activity. He began to believe that man is capable of knowing the natural landscape of the universe, even his own nature. Exalting the dignity of a person, considering him as the highest value, created a new spiritual environment for the further development of the ideal of freedom. The roots of

ABSTRACT

Philosophical concepts of nature and society are important in examining the concept of man. Human life is directly connected with these two concepts-categories. In this process, there are a number of reasons that are not related to the human factor, and they are a decisive force in determining a person's lifestyle, happiness or unhappiness.

Renaissance natural philosophy go back to the ancient Greek philosophical heritage, in particular to Platonism, Stoic pantheism, and Ionic philosophy.

Experts consider the European Enlightenment a "philosophical, social, moral concept", an ideology that is the basis of a new worldview. The core of the new ideology is the view that "only human intelligence can change the world." In fact, the ideas of the Enlightenment had a serious impact on the further development of social consciousness: starting from the XXIII century, the views of materialism began to conquer the minds of more and more people. This ideology, which came into the world as a product of certain social conditions, made radical changes in all spheres of society, especially in literature and art. In Europe, under the influence of Enlightenment ideas, literature based on new aesthetic principles was formed, based on the belief that "ideological literature capable of changing the world and man is needed." In other words, the social ideal of the Enlightenment - "building a society in

accordance with human nature and "mind" became the aesthetic ideal of the Enlightenment literature. This required the literature to change accordingly. Among these changes, the most important is the "falling down" of the ideal, as a result of which the concepts of artistry and beauty were seriously revised.

Although the main characters in the tragedies "Macbeth" and "Abulfayz Khan" are selfish, murderers and people at the highest level of society, the fate of the state and people should not be connected with a single person. A person is educated and brought up by the society, the person who aspires to power and manages it relies, first of all, on the support and goodwill of the representatives of a certain category or class operating in this society. Happiness or unhappiness, peace or war occurs only because of the conditions and opportunities created by society. Both the plight and perfection of the main characters are directly related to society; the author alone in the tragedy thinks on behalf of the people and judges based on his ideological intention.

The author, more than anyone, feels the spirit of the era, which reflects reality. It is this closeness that forces him to write. Under the slogan of Khoja Hafiz, "Let's tear down the old and build a new one", reformism and creativity are hidden.

Man cannot be free because he has duties and responsibilities. He always has to go against his will, if this criterion is violated, the family, society, and the whole relationship will be destroyed.

Man is always bound to something, he is a creature not adapted to infinity. Man lives in night and day, seasons and finally society. No one can break this order, it is impossible to leave the first and go to the

next. Therefore, the reality and the events happening in it concern a person. The situation in the society determines the spiritual image of the people, the progress or decline of the state also depends on the worldview of the people. This is the point that unites the tragedies of Shakespeare and Fitrat.

It is impossible to create a work by separating humanity from society, history, time, and space. In the characters of Macbeth and Abulfayzkhan, he represented the inner-inner-hidden world of practical actions that occur as a result of human sociality, rationality, ideology and faith. They cannot be cut off from society for reasons beyond their control, not only society, but cage after cage, they are forced to attract attention, examine and question themselves, confess their sins and answer for their actions. Regardless of the nature of any event, action, or process in society, it always leaves a mark. Amazing historical developments give new spirit, new idea, dream, hope and strength to the members of the society. The entire complexity of the era and society was reflected in the work of the artist, who was able to come out of the shell of a single person, as if in a mirror.

Lady Macbeth, the epitome of a woman, wife and mother, is not afraid of anything, compassion is alien to her, she has forgotten what even the feeling of love is.

A vivid reflection of the Renaissance ideal of man. King Macduff is the bravest, fairest, bravest, wisest, noblest of the tragic characters in the tragedy, while the nobles (Rodrigo, Graziano, Lodovico, Cassio, etc.) are dull, ordinary little people, the bright and honorable image of Othello is clearly visible. stand out, it was not for nothing that Desdemona chose Othello and not them. Iago is also a representative of the

Renaissance, he also went through many worries and difficulties together with Othello, has a lot of experience, but he drew completely different conclusions from it. If he brought up Othello to face difficulties, he also brought up Iago. But for Iago, the value of a person is measured by his position in society and money

The reason why the dramatist portrays the typical representative of the humanist of the Renaissance in the role of a prince, in our opinion, if we bring to our eyes the life and system of that time, the bitter truth told by Hamlet's language, the question arises: who could say the *zakarkhandas*, what kind of person could say it on the social ladder. Of course, it is not natural for any scientist, humanist, philosopher, courtier to reveal the revealing truths told by Hamlet. Among the main characters of Shakespeare's tragedies, only Hamlet embodies the highest human qualities and serves to fight evil for the sake of human happiness. Therefore, Hamlet, the noblest representative of European humanism, is closest to our time and contemporaries. Shakespeare and his contemporaries did not know the concepts of "feudalism" and "capitalism", but they knew well what and who brought misfortune to society, people and individuals. The main social causes of modern discontent, Shakespeare's tragedy and Hamlet's melancholy were also in the conflict between the ideals of humanists and the times.

In his works, Shakespeare not only describes subjective tragic events, but also describes objective tragic situations on a national and global scale. In Shakespeare's tragedies, not only the tragedy of individual persons is presented, their content is the tragedy of life in general. Tragic characters such as Hamlet, Othello, Lear, Macbeth,

Brutus, Coriolanus, Antony, and Timon are representatives of different times, peoples, and classes, and their tragedy is the tragedy of the humanity of that time. In the playwright's tragedies, "why is a person unhappy, what prevents his happiness?" questions. To answer these questions, the artist examines life in every way. Shakespeare's tragedies include friendship and love between individuals, society, state, international relations, and various aspects of life in general. The wealth of life experience in the playwright amazes a person, while watching or reading his works on stage, Renaissance England is fully embodied before our eyes. There is almost no field that the playwright does not know and does not correctly reflect in his works: it is not for nothing that he is called a lawyer, geographer, philosopher, naturalist and scientist. But the essence of Shakespeare's tragedies is not only in the realistic depiction of the picture of the period. The playwright reveals the most complex dialectics of the human spirit and how the tragedy of life affected him. In his works, Iason is not a passive figure crushed under the influence of external factors. even in the drama there is no "environment" in the mechanistic sense. In Shakespeare's dramas, there is only one factor - man and his relationship to other people, nature, society and state system. But the state, classes also have their own characteristics, power, are depicted in a certain image, even society, natural forces are depicted in human form. That is why Shakespeare's humanism is not an abstract concept, but the very basis of his work. Of course, Shakespeare enjoyed the achievements of the great scientists and philosophers of the Renaissance, Montaigne, Bacon, Bruno, and the science

and philosophy of that time in general. Shakespeare, as a representative of the last period of the Renaissance, on the one hand, was a witness to the failure of humanist dreams, and on the other hand, he did not lose his faith in human strength, ability, value of humanism, and optimism. Therefore, there are elements of both tragedy and heroism in his work. Belief in human power and the future created heroism and did not allow tragedy and pessimism to dominate, and made it possible to make philosophical and artistic generalizations that have not yet been published in world literature. Shakespeare

described the most complex period of European history and created new types of tragedies that have not yet been seen in English dramaturgy in terms of problems and style. The large scale of Shakespeare's tragedies was the fact that the reasons that gave rise to this genre were European, the transition from one social formation to another, from one period to another, and a product of a period when spiritual development reached a high level. But only a certain circle of people could enjoy this rich culture. Due to the illiteracy of the main masses, the Renaissance was achieved.

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